

**MAPPING OF VEGETATION COVER INDICATORS OF SOILS OF
JIZZAKH REGION USING GIS TECHNOLOGIES (ON THE EXAMPLE
OF TYPICAL IRRIGATED SEROZEM AND NEWLY IRRIGATED
SEROZEM-MEADOW SOILS).**

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Annotation

This article describes the vegetation cover indicators of typical irrigated serozem and newly irrigated serozem-meadow soils distributed in the Jizzakh region. According to it, it is observed that the vegetation cover indicators of typical irrigated serozem soils increase towards the mountain slopes and the upper part of the mountain, while, on the contrary, they are somewhat lower on newly irrigated serozem-meadow soils, based on a certain regularity. These data are based on mapping data obtained using GIS technologies.

Keywords: Soil, irrigated typical, serozem-meadow, NDVI, geoinformation technologies, remote sensing.

Introduction. Today, GIS technology is based on a comprehensive, multidimensional context, and also helps to monitor and manage changes in various fields, as well as process valuable data in both public and private organizations[1].

Geographic information technologies are becoming increasingly important in various fields, including digital maps, geospatial databases, land management, urban planning, and transportation. [2].

Soil moisture, especially surface moisture, is one of its most important indicators. The combination of surface soil temperature and vegetation cover further enhances the ability to obtain information about soil moisture [3].

Remote sensing of soil is essential for monitoring and mapping the existing vegetation cover on the soil. Today, monitoring the distribution and phenology of plants based on various vegetation index indicators is the most widely used

work. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is one of the most commonly used indicators [4].

Research object and methods. The research objects were selected as typical irrigated serozem soils of the “Laylak Uya” massif of the Zamin district of the Jizzakh region and newly irrigated serozem-meadow soils distributed in the “Kazakhstan” massif of the Arnasay district. Analysis based on geographic information systems was carried out using the ArcGIS program and its Geostatistical Analyst modules.

Research results and their analysis. According to it, it was found that the vegetation cover index of the typical serozem irrigated soils of the Zamin district is slightly higher. The northern part of the study area is characterized by a high proportion of areas with a vegetation cover index of 0,23-0,39 while the southern parts of the area are occupied by areas with a vegetation index of 0,051-0,22. Based on this data, a 1:10,000 scale map of the NDVI index was created using a GIS program. (Picture-1).

Factors such as the area's vegetation cover, the ability of plants to photosynthesize and their biological productivity, soil moisture content, and the relationship of plants to other growth phases also affect NDVI indicators[5].

It was found that the vegetation cover indicators are slightly lower in the soils distributed in the “Kazakhstan” massif of Arnasay district, where the study was conducted. In particular, the areas belonging to the vegetation index group of 0,021-0,2 are distinguished by the predominance of areas, while areas with a vegetation index of 0,38-0,55 are found to be distributed in both the northern and southern parts of the region. Based on this data, a 1:10,000 scale map of the NDVI index was created using a GIS program. (Picture-2)

Picture-1. Vegetation cover map of typical serozem soils irrigated in the "Laylak Uya" massif of Zamin district.

Picture-2. Vegetation cover map of newly irrigated serozem-meadow soils of the "Kazakhstan" massif in Arnasay district.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that the climatic conditions of the studied regions are different, and the density of vegetation varies sharply throughout the year. The "Laylak uya" massif is located in a high-altitude region and is characterized by high soil moisture depending on air temperature, the amount of annual precipitation is higher than in the "Kazakhstan" massif, the proportion of areas with a vegetation cover index of 0,23-0,39 in the northern part is higher, and the content of humus and nutrients in the soil is higher than in the "Kazakhstan" massif, as determined by the NDVI indicator using the GIS program. Both selected areas were divided into groups based on the vegetation cover indicators on irrigated soils, and a 1:10,000 scale map was created using GIS software based on the NDVI indicator.

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